

Signal Transduction Systems: The Debate over the Classification of the Human Nitric Oxide Gasoreceptor Soluble Guanylate Cyclase

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

Running title: Signal transduction systems and sGC

Keywords: cell signaling, gasocrine signaling, signal transduction systems, receptor, gasoreceptor, soluble guanylate cyclase, nitric oxide, gasotransmitters, gaseous signaling molecule

Nitric oxide (NO) is a gaseous signaling molecule and well known gasotransmitter.¹ In order to bring together researchers from different disciplines, I recently proposed that nitric oxide serve as both a gasocrine signaling molecule and a non-essential gasotransmitter.² Several nitric oxide receptors (gasoreceptors) have been identified in various organisms.³ Among these gasoreceptors, the human soluble guanylate cyclase (sGC) is one of the most well-studied.

One open question is under which type of signal transduction system sGC should be classified? A protein containing sensing and signaling domains in different regions functions as a one-component signal transduction system.⁴ I also proposed that proteins with overlapping sensing and signaling domains can function as a proto-component signal transduction system.⁵ If sGC exhibits enzymatic activity, it could function as a one-component or proto-component signal transduction system. However, sGC is a heterodimer composed of two subunits: α 1 (GUCY1A3) and β 1 (GUCY1B3). Only the β 1 subunit contains the heme nitric oxide and oxygen-binding (H-NOX) domain, while the catalytic domain is formed jointly by both the subunits.⁶⁻⁸ Therefore, a sGC heterodimer cannot be considered an example of either the one-component or proto-component signal transduction systems since both subunits share the catalytic domain. By comparison, the *Escherichia coli* oxygen gasoreceptor DosP phosphodiesterase is a homodimer, but its catalytic domain is not formed through dimerization.⁹ Thus, DosP can still be classified as a gasoreceptor in a one-component signal transduction system.

Next, consider the split-component signal transduction system that I recently proposed.¹⁰ This system is exemplified by the mammalian glucokinase regulator (GCKR, also known as glucokinase regulatory protein - GKR) and GCK (glucokinase). The GCKR-GCK complex formation and GCK catalytic activity status depend on the ligand binding to GKR. The ligands are fructose 1-phosphate and fructose 6-phosphate, and the signal transducer is GCK.¹¹ However, sGC does not fit into the split-component model since its catalytic domain is shared between the two subunits and cannot be separated. Therefore, whether sGC could be classified as a gasoreceptor in a co-component signal transduction system remains a topic of debate.¹²

REFERENCES

1. Ignarro LJ, Freeman B. Nitric Oxide: Biology and Pathobiology. Academic Press; 2017.
2. Anbalagan S. Oxygen is an essential gasotransmitter directly sensed via protein gasoreceptors. *Animal Models and Experimental Medicine* 2024; 7:189–93.
3. Aono S. Gas Sensing in Cells. Royal Society of Chemistry; 2017.
4. Ulrich LE, Koonin EV, Zhulin IB. One-component systems dominate signal transduction in prokaryotes. *Trends Microbiol* 2005; 13:52–6.
5. Anbalagan S. Proto-component signal transduction systems. Zenodo; 2025 [cited 2025 July 22]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/15423964>
6. Allerston CK, von Delft F, Gileadi O. Crystal Structures of the Catalytic Domain of Human Soluble Guanylate Cyclase. *PLoS One* 2013; 8:e57644.
7. Horst BG, Yokom AL, Rosenberg DJ, Morris KL, Hammel M, Hurley JH, Marletta MA. Allosteric activation of the nitric oxide receptor soluble guanylate cyclase mapped by cryo-electron microscopy. *Elife* 2019; 8:e50634.
8. Kang Y, Liu R, Wu J-X, Chen L. Structural insights into the mechanism of human soluble guanylate cyclase. *Nature* 2019; 574:206–10.
9. Wu W, Kumar P, Brautigam CA, Tso S-C, Baniyadi HR, Kober DL, Gilles-Gonzalez M-A. Structures of the multi-domain oxygen sensor DosP: remote control of a c-di-GMP phosphodiesterase by a regulatory PAS domain. *Nat Commun* 2024; 15:9653.
10. Anbalagan S. Split-component signal transduction systems. Zenodo; 2025 [cited 2025 Sept 17]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/15393702>
11. Beck T, Miller BG. Structural basis for regulation of human glucokinase by glucokinase regulatory protein. *Biochemistry* 2013; 52:6232–9.
12. Kinch LN, Cong Q, Jaishankar J, Orth K. Co-component signal transduction systems: Fast-evolving virulence regulation cassettes discovered in enteric bacteria. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2022; 119:e2203176119.